

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FOOD INTOLERANCES AND ALLERGIES IN AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

Boboc D.,

*Doctoral student, Doctoral School Institute, Ovidius University Constanța, Romania
Maria Montessori School Center for Inclusive Education – Constanța, Romania*

Cojocaru M.,

*Titu Maiorescu University, Faculty of Medicine – Bucharest, Romania
Academy of Romanian Scientists Ilfov 3, 050044 Bucharest, Romania*

Roșoiu N.

*Doctoral Supervisor Institute of Doctoral Schools Ovidius University Constanța, Romania
Academia of Romanian Scientists Ilfov 3, 050044 Bucharest, Romania
Ovidius University Constanța, Faculty of Medicine, Romania
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Background Autism is often associated with immune system problems, gastrointestinal problems, and changes in the gut microbiome. This can be caused by a sensitivity to certain foods or even a food allergy. Several previous studies have investigated the relationship between allergic conditions and autism spectrum disorder (ASD). This disorder remains throughout life, directly affecting not only the diagnosed individuals, but also their families, who must adapt to the new life context and make decisions about the treatment and therapies necessary for recovery. According to recent research, the prevalence of autism spectrum disorder has increased by 123% in the past decade. The alarming increase in the prevalence of autism is directly proportional to the responsibility of parents and professionals to identify effective treatments and therapies.

Objectives Assessment of the state of health. Determining the intestinal microbiome is important for children with autism because imbalances at this level can seriously affect the state of homeostasis. Material and methods Analyzing the main biochemical markers through laboratory analyses. The biochemical imbalance can influence the symptoms in autism and it is important that the therapeutic intervention must be carried out on all the affected levels.

Results After analyzing the case study, we notice that after starting the treatment with multi-strain probiotic and vitamin D, the symptoms of autism improved. A reduction in asthma attacks and an increase in immunity were also observed. The nutritionist recommended the introduction of a ketogenic diet as well as a diet rich in foods that contain vitamin D.

Conclusion Our results suggest that gastrointestinal disorders and food sensitivities may be more common in children with autism spectrum disorders, and the application of dietary diets may help the autistic child to improve their health.

Keywords: autism, asthma, food allergy, healthy lifestyle, gut microbiome

Introductory notions

According to the United States Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC, 2020), autism spectrum disorder (ASD) has become a common disorder, affecting 1 in 54 children, that is usually diagnosed in childhood (Medavarapu, 2019). People diagnosed with ASD often receive controversial treatments (Simpson, 2005), mainly because the beneficiaries are not sufficiently informed, but also because of the lack of an entity that regulates these forms of treatment. According to Simpson's definition, a controversial treatment is any method or strategy that has not been supported by scientific evidence. These forms of treatment are called alternative therapies, and in English - complementary and alternative medicine and therapy. It is important that parents of children with ASD choose in an informed manner the correct form of therapy and are informed about the lack of positive effects of alternative treatments and their disadvantages. By looking at these forms of scientifically unproven therapies and knowing that there is no cure yet to change this life condition, the decision-making process will be easier and clearer. Gluten-

free casein-free diet involves dietary elimination of certain proteins such as gluten and casein. This therapy is based on the theory that the accumulation of peptides and toxins in the body affects the proper functioning of the brain. Incomplete processing of peptides acts like opioids, reduces pain sensitivity and increases the severity of specific behaviors in children with ASD (Baspinar, 2020). However, studies have not shown mechanisms to support this theory. It is a myth that a gluten-free and casein-free diet is risk-free (Mari-Bauset, 2014), so parents choose this approach without having the big picture. There are no conclusive studies demonstrating the lack of risk associated with the elimination of these proteins from the body (Dosman, 2013). Also, families who choose this therapy may face financial difficulties and an expensive diet. Currently, there is insufficient scientific evidence to recommend a gluten-free diet as a treatment for autism spectrum disorder (Buie, 2013). A review of studies in this area found no benefit for ASD symptoms (Piwowarczyk, 2017). Furthermore, clinical trials did not detect behavioral changes (Gonzales-Domenech, 2019), alt-

though a post-intervention diet effect was observed, associating behavioral changes with urinary beta-casomorphin levels. Autism spectrum disorder is a complex neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by deficits in social interaction, language and communication, as well as the presence of limited repetitive behaviors. The etiology of ASD includes both genetic and environmental risk factors, and it is estimated that up to 40–50% of the variance responsible for ASD can be attributed to environmental risk factors. Allergies are often a major problem in patients with autism and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

Doctors who regularly treat autistic patients often find that a disproportionate number of these children also have chronic allergy problems, such as: rhinitis (nasal congestion), sinusitis (sinus infection), recurrent ear infections, otitis media (fluid in the middle ear), asthma, eczema (inflammation of the skin). New research suggests that the immune system plays an important role in autism. This means that people with autism are twice as likely to have food allergies, skin allergies or respiratory allergies (Lyall et al., 2015).

Parents of children with ASD who have gastrointestinal symptoms often report improvements in certain behaviors and resolution of gastrointestinal symptoms after implementing dietary interventions such as a casein-free/gluten-free diet. Such observations suggest that food allergies may influence behavioral symptoms in some children with autism spectrum disorders (Guifeng et al., 2018). Food allergies, in particular, can worsen behavioral symptoms because the child cannot communicate their discomfort very effectively. Aberrations of the immune system are one of the frequently observed problems, including frequent infections, altered cytokine levels, and increased prevalence of autoimmune diseases. It has been suggested that the association of food allergy with autism spectrum disorder may be a major reason for the high prevalence of gastrointestinal problems in children with autism spectrum disorder (Onore et al., 2012).

Children with autism may not be able to communicate their discomfort when dealing with an allergic reaction. You may notice changes in behavior such as becoming more extreme; they can even start to dissolve or cause adverse reactions to certain foods. Here are some signs: irritability, sleep problems, difficulty concentrating, repetitive behavior, hyperactivity.

Researchers from the Department of Epidemiology at the University of Iowa found that 11 percent of children with autism had food allergies, compared to 4 percent of neurotypical children. Almost 19% of children with autism spectrum disorder had respiratory allergies than other children. Many had skin allergies; this rate was nearly 17%, compared to nearly 10% of non-spectrum children (Nardone, Elliot, 2016). However, there is no proven link between allergies and autism or that allergies are associated with the development of autism disorders. Food intolerance is a common problem in children with autism. This can cause discomfort and increase behavior problems. Although an intolerance is not the same as an allergy, they have similar treatments (Billeci et al., 2015).

In recent years, experts have discovered that the bacteria in the intestines affect the development of diseases and our mood. While this science is still in its infancy, researchers have found that the gut microbiome of children with autism is different. Certain foods can cause discomfort, pain and fear in people with autism spectrum disorders. Autistic children are more likely to suffer from constipation, diarrhea or stomach pain. Some types of food allergies are more common in children with autism than others. People with autism are more likely to be allergic to the following foods: egg protein, soy protein, casein or milk protein, corn protein, gluten or wheat protein (Vargas et al., 2005; Gottfried et al., 2015).

Immune dysfunction is a possible link between environmental risk factors and autism spectrum disorder. Children with autism spectrum disorders have often been reported to have symptoms of immune system disorders, such as frequent infections and an increased prevalence of autoimmune diseases. In addition, maternal infection, inflammatory cytokines, and autoimmune diseases during pregnancy have also been associated with autism spectrum disorder in children in some studies (Theoharides et al., 2016; Moaaz et al., 2016).

Treating allergies often appears to improve not only the child's health, but can also have a positive effect on function and parameters of autism spectrum disorder, including eye contact, joint attention, social interaction, and language processing function.

Conclusions

Autistic spectrum disorder is a disease that affects a person's development, especially in social interaction, causing behavioral problems and lack of communication skills. Children with ASD are generally underdiagnosed and undertreated for allergic diseases as well as other non-allergic diseases that are common in children. Anaphylaxis can be a life-threatening condition. A child on the autism spectrum with recurrent infections deserves an immune evaluation for immunodeficiency. An autistic child with eczema, chronic nasal symptoms, asthma, significant gastrointestinal symptoms, or recurrent respiratory infections requires a more thorough evaluation to identify whether they are suffering from various food allergies or intolerances.

CASE STUDY

A.V.M - boy, born in the city of Constanta on 19.02.2018. At the moment, the family lives in the city of Ovidiu, Constanța county.

Diagnosis:

1. ADHD
2. Infantile autism

Personal anamnesis:

During the pregnancy, the mother was very stressed because she experienced a death in the family. She was legally married to the father of the child for 6 years, he being sick with a cancerous tumor in the spine, diagnosed 1 year before the birth of the child. She was not a smoker and did not consume alcohol. The child's birth was on time, but by caesarean section due to complications that arose at the last moment. The APGAR score at birth was 9. The child was born with a congenital malformation on the left ear, which was detected after birth through audio tests performed by

the attending doctors. He started walking at the age of 2 years and was crawling normally at the age of 1 and a half years.

Somatic and thoracic development, within normal limits: normal appearance, proportional body.

Family Anamnesis:

He is the first child in the family. At birth, the mother was 25 years old and the father 36 years old. The mother worked at a grocery store, and the father was retired due to illness. They lived together. The parents separated in 2021, 3 years after the boy was born. A week after the divorce papers were issued, the child's father died, the causes being the illness he suffered. Their lifestyle was orderly and balanced, without arguments but only with small misunderstandings. While the mother was at work, the minor remained in the care of the maternal grandmother, who helped him a lot. The child's relationship with the other family members was good, he being very close to his maternal grandmother. The child shows emotional disturbances and increased psychomotor agitation, impatience and poor concentration. He is not interested in things that make loud noises, being frightened by them. Controls were carried out by ENT doctors from the Constanța County Clinical Hospital, to be continued at the Audionova ENT clinic, where audio tests were performed while awake and asleep. The audio tests performed showed that he hears very little with his left ear, and the right one is in perfect condition.

Recommendations:

- Implantation of the affected ear with a cochlear implant,

- Speech therapy to develop language,

The implantation was carried out at the hospital in Târgu Mureș. The controls were carried out at the Marie Curie children's hospital in Bucharest and the behavioral assessment was carried out at several speech therapists and psychiatrists in Constanta.

The child has now started to develop his language by repeating words and forming short phrases, through speech therapy 3 times a week for 1 hour. He presents, in addition to hearing and language problems, bronchial asthma, frequent colds because he has deficient immune system and has frequent gastrointestinal problems. Because of intestinal transit disorders such as constipation that seemed to worsen autism symptoms, he went to a psychiatrist in Iasi. The doctor suggested him to perform several laboratory analyses, including the analysis of the intestinal microbiome, which, according to the doctor, would be behind the child's serious problems. After performing the analyses, it was observed that there are several biochemical markers that are below normal values. In the case of vitamin D, the situation is worse because the value obtained is 14 nanograms, and the minimum normal value is 30 nanograms. The analysis of the intestinal microbiome did not turn out well, which required sending the results to the doctor in Iași, who subsequently sent him the treatment. The large amount of positive lipopolysaccharide bacteria required a two-week probiotic treatment. One month after the start of the treatment, the mother had a dysbiosis analysis. The analysis showed an improve-

ment of the problems that initially appeared in the intestinal microbiome. It was recommended to start a ketogenic diet under the guidance of the nutritionist because gluten intolerance was detected. The doctor also created a recuperative nutritional plan to increase the value of vitamin D. After a period of 3 months from the start of the diet, it was noticed that the symptoms were reduced, the intestinal transit was regulated, the immunity increased, even the bronchial asthma improved.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the study was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be interpreted as a potential conflict of interest.

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